

Studies in Galvanoluminescence : Part III. Production and Chemical Effects of Anode Glow

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Manuscript received 4 November 1974 ; revised 9 February 1976 ; accepted 19 March 1976

Galvanoluminescence is a new type of electrolysis accompanied by appearance of luminosity at one of the electrodes and developed spontaneously in course of ordinary electrolysis at a suitably high voltage. Though there is a preferential tendency for the glow to appear at cathode rather than at anode, by suitably adjusting the experimental condition, the glow can be produced at the anode also. The condition for the production of glow at the anode and the nature of glow with a variety of aqueous electrolytes have been described. Highly interesting are the chemical effects of anode glow in that the yield exceeds the Faraday law value and that the gas liberated at the glowing anode is a liberal mixture of oxygen and hydrogen. A critical survey of the chemical results produced by anode glow in different aqueous electrolytes has been presented. A comparison of the results of anode glow with those of cathode glow has been made.

DURING ordinary electrolysis at a voltage sufficiently higher than the decomposition potential, a spontaneous transition to an electrode luminescence phenomenon called 'galvanoluminescence' or 'glow-electrolysis' occurs. It has been found that there is a much stronger preference for the glow to appear at the cathode than at the anode. In our earlier papers of the series we reported the results of our investigation on production and chemical effects of cathode glow process^{1,2}. However by suitable adjustment of the experimental conditions, the glow can at will be made to appear at the anode. It has been found³ what is important in deciding whether the glow will appear at the cathode or at the anode on the breakdown of ordinary electrolysis is the *relative surface area* of the two electrodes (not their relative thinness or diameter). Thus under right conditions it has been observed that if the surface of the anode is sufficiently smaller than that of the cathode, galvanoluminescence spontaneously develops at the anode on the breakdown of normal electrolysis. We report herein the results of our investigation on production and chemical effects of anode glow in different types of aqueous electrolytes and compare the results with those of the cathode glow process.

Experimental

Anode glow process was conveniently studied with the same experimental set-up as in the previous paper under the following conditions : electrolyte, 0.4-0.6N solution ; pressure, atmospheric ; electrodes, platinum wire, diameter of anode, 0.35 mm ; length of anode, 4 mm ; diameter of cathode, 0.35 mm ; length of cathode, 15mm ; distance of each of the electrodes below the free surface of the electrolyte, 4-5 cm ; voltage applied between the electrodes, 200-260 volts D. C. supplied from a bank of lead accumulators in series.

To analyse the liberated electrode gases, further arrangement was made to connect one or both of the

gas outlets through a system of gas burettes to a Hempel type oxygen analyzer where oxygen content in the sample gas was estimated by absorption in alkaline pyrogallol. Hydrogen was estimated by explosion method and this was done in a separate unit. A Lingane type gas coulometer⁷ fitted with suitably large platinum electrodes containing 0.1M K_2SO_4 was included in the circuit to measure electricity passed and to compute the average current strength during glow when yields of chemical products were studied.

Production of anode glow : The spontaneous transition from ordinary electrolysis to anode glow can be seen from a typical current-time behaviour (Fig. 1) for

Fig. 1

0.6(N) Na_2SO_4 solution. Initially, current as usual rises more or less linearly with time and normal electrolysis occurs with a profusion of fine bubbles of gases leaving both the electrodes. When the point B is reached, the cell operation is disturbed and the symptoms characteristic of the so-called 'transition period'¹ develop in a milder condition. When the point C is reached an instantaneous change takes place. The current steeply drops to a much lower value (point D) with simultaneous appearance of bright yellow luminescence at the anode. The anode is completely enveloped in a gaseous film. The anode gas no longer evolves in streams of fine bubbles, but in spurts of big bubbles. During anode glow the cathode behaves in the normal way. At this stage, the current reading is stabilised (variation ± 15 mA) and the glow is steady and self-sustaining.

Using our standard conditions, anode glow was successfully developed with various aqueous electrolytes. The glow so produced is confined very close to the anode surface, and does not spread out into the entire vapour mantle around the electrode. This glow can be operated in milder condition and is more easily controllable than cathode glow. However in most cases, the anode glow is of the same colour as that of cathode glow. Thus with sodium salts bright yellow, with potassium salts pink-violet, with barium salts light green or deep violet, with strontium salts deep violet, with ammonium salts and acids red (with violet tinge) glow have been observed.

It has been found in general that the values for current maxima (pt. C) are within 500–650 mA for a good number of sodium, potassium, barium, strontium and ammonium salts, and higher in the case of alkalis (~ 850 mA) and strong inorganic acids (~ 1400 mA). However, the current reading on anode glow (pt. D) remains within 50–130 mA with all these electrolytes (cf. cathode glow current which is usually 100–200 mA).

Chemical results of anode luminescence: Liberation of hydrogen at anode: From preliminary analysis of the gas liberated at the glowing anode it has been found that as in the case of cathode glow² chemical effects of anode glow are markedly different from those of ordinary electrolysis and show similar non-Faradaic features. Thus during anode luminescence produced under our conditions, the volume of anode gas exceeds the Faraday law value and this anode gas contains a substantial percentage of hydrogen (vide Table 1). Apart from these two common non-Faradaic features, many novel products depending upon the nature of substrate present are often formed. However, the degree of the non-Faradaic aspects is less strongly developed in anode glow than in cathode glow. From an analysis of the results with several electrolytes it appears that as in the case of cathode glow², the reactions involved at the luminescent anode are of two types: (i) charge transfer processes giving Faradaic results and (ii) breaking up of solvent molecules and other suitable substrates, if any, present or produced near the anode giving non-Faradaic results. During anode luminescence the cathode behaves normally and gives results consistent with Faraday's law.

However, on electrolysis of many salts (e. g. nitrite) acids produced in the anolyte being not very stable chemical results at anode are often complex in nature. Besides, even in ordinary electrolysis of electrolytes such as chloride, the anodic product is not pure oxygen. For the sake of simplicity, chemical study on anode glow has been restricted to those electrolytes which normally liberate only oxygen at anode and anolytes of which are stable under ordinary electrolysis. Depending on whether the anolyte of such an electrolyte is stable under anode glow condition or not, a classification of electrolytes into inert and non-inert types has been made. Results obtained with such electrolytes including ammonium salts are described below.

(a) *Inert type electrolytes: alkali metal phosphates, borates and bases:* The volume of the gas liberated at the luminescent anode is greater than the Faraday law value and this anode gas usually contains substantial percentage (6–20%) of hydrogen (vide Table 1a). On comparing these results with the corresponding ones of cathode glow², it is seen that the degree of the non-Faradaic features is much less acute under anode glow than under cathode glow. The table also shows that the non-Faradaic aspects are more strongly developed with alkalis than with salts. As a result of anode glow in such systems no new species at least in amounts sufficient for qualitative detection, is produced in the anolyte. In fact, if one allows for breakup of water molecules into hydrogen and oxygen in addition to usual Faradaic oxidation of OH^- to O_2 , a material balance can be achieved within the limits of experimental error.

(b) *Non-inert alkali metal and alkaline earth metal salts and acids: sulphates and nitrates:* With such salts and acids, it is generally observed that the deviation for the anode gas volume from Faraday law value is significantly higher than that with inert salts (vide Table 1b). In fact, anode gases with such electrolytes contain more oxygen than that could be accounted for by decomposition of H_2O and Faradaic oxidation of OH^- to O_2 and the anolyte solutions give positive tests for SO_2 with sulphates and HNO_2 with nitrates. It appears that the acid present or produced in the anolyte gets decomposed under anode glow condition and causes higher anode gas volume with production of new species in the anolyte. Thus with sulphates, acid sulphates and H_2SO_4 we get O_2 and SO_2 from decomposition of H_2SO_4 , and with nitrates and HNO_3 we get O_2 , HNO_2 , NO_2 and NO from decomposition of HNO_3 . It is likely that the metal nitrates also themselves get dissociated to produce more oxygen. From the table we see that the trend for the higher oxygen content hence lower hydrogen percentage in the anode gas is more strongly manifested as one passes from sulphate through acid sulphate to H_2SO_4 solutions. This appears to be due to parallel increases of acid concentration in the anolyte resulting in greater decomposition of the acid to O_2 and lower percentage of H_2 in the anode gas. The table also shows that this trend for lower hydrogen percentage is more pronounced with nitrates than with sulphates. This is expected since HNO_3 is more

easily decomposed than H_2SO_4 and metal nitrates may themselves undergo decomposition under anode glow condition.

(c) *Ammonium salts*: $(NH_4)_2SO_4$: Results of anode glow with $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ solutions are highly interesting. Apart from considerably greater positive deviation from Faraday law value with $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ than with other sulphates, the percentage of hydrogen in the gas liberated at the glowing anode is significantly much higher with $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ than with any other electrolyte used in the present investigation (vide Table 1c). Further SO_2 or SO_3^- can be detected in the anolyte solution. However, more interesting is the fact that the total volume of oxygen in the anode gas (7.1 ml) is considerably less than that would have been liberated on the basis of Faraday's law (13.8 ml). Moreover, the anode gas contains a substantial percentage (~30%) of nitrogen. From an analysis of the results it appears that under anode glow condition Faradaic process involves a much greater oxidation of NH_4^+ to N_2 than that of OH^- to O_2 causing such lower oxygen content and the non-Faradaic process as usual involves breaking up of H_2O and H_2SO_4 molecules (produced in anolyte) giving H_2 , O_2 and SO_2 . It is not also unlikely that some $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ may get decomposed to give N_2 , SO_2 and NH_3 , the latter subsequently dissociating into N_2 and H_2 .

The results given in the tables are representative figures only. From quite a good number of results it has been found that the average current strength varies over a 15 mA range when the figures $V_A/V_{FA}\%$ and $V_{H_2}/V_A\%$ sweep over within a 5% and a 2.5% range respectively.

Thus we see that although the positive deviation from Faraday's law and occurrence of substantial percentage of hydrogen in the anode gas are common features of chemical effects of anode glow, the results may be significantly influenced by the nature of the electrolyte present.

Chemical effects of anode and cathodic galvanoluminescence: Although the general features of chemical effects of anode glow and cathode glow are similar, as pointed out earlier, the former is far less productive than the latter and that the magnitude of deviation from Faraday's law and the extent of co-liberation are much less strongly manifested in the former than in the latter. From a comparison of the chemical results of cathode glow and anode glow produced on a 6 mm wire electrode with Na_2HPO_4 solution at 260 volts under identical conditions, it has been found that the amount of non-Faradaic reaction during cathode glow is about 9 times that during anode glow (vide Table 2).

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL RESULTS OF ANODE GLOW

Electrolyte	Voltage applied (volts) D.C.	Av. current during glow (mA)	V_F (ml)	V_{FA} (ml)	V_A (ml)	V_A/V_{FA} %	V_{H_2} (ml)	V_{H_2}/V_A %
(a) Inert type electrolytes								
NaH_2PO_4 1.0(N)	216	113	83.2	27.73	30.8	111	1.94	6.3
Na_2HPO_4 1.0(N)	216	128	88.2	29.40	32.9	112	2.33	7.1
$Na_2B_4O_7$ 0.8(N)	216	87	103.8	34.60	35.3	102	0.60	1.7
$NaOH$ 0.4(N)	216	120	85.3	28.43	34.7	122	4.40	12.7
KOH 0.4(N)	216	100	69.3	23.10	32.6	141	6.26	19.2
(b) Non-inert electrolytes								
Na_2SO_4 0.8(N)	216	105	74.5	24.84	32.3	130	3.00	9.3
K_2SO_4 0.6(N)	216	75	77.4	25.80	35.1	136	2.74	7.8
$KHSO_4$ 0.6(N)	216	110	65.0	21.67	33.4	154	2.34	7.0
H_2SO_4 0.9(N)	216	50	60.7	20.23	34.0	168	1.94	5.7
$NaNO_3$ 0.6(N)	216	84	41.9	13.97	32.7	234	1.60	4.9
KNO_3 0.6(N)	216	51	44.2	14.73	33.2	225	1.86	5.6
$Ba(NO_3)_2$ 0.7(N)	210	81	42.0	14.00	34.2	244	1.54	4.5
$Sr(NO_3)_2$ 0.7(N)	216	55	41.0	13.67	35.3	258	1.66	4.7
HNO_3 0.9(N)	216	72	28.8	39.60	37.2	388	1.60	4.3

(c) Ammonium sulphate as electrolyte

$(NH_4)_2SO_4$ 0.9(N) 220 54 41.4 13.80 34.8 252 17.20 49.4

V_F - Vol. of total gas liberated in the coulometer

V_{FA} - $1/3 V_F$ → anode gas vol. acc. to Faraday's law

V_A - anode gas vol. actually liberated

V_{H_2} - Vol of H_2 found in V_A . V_{H_2} is two-third of the contraction in Vol. on exploding the anode gas.

TABLE 2—A COMPARISON OF CHEMICAL RESULTS OF CATHODE GLOW AND ANODE GLOW

Glow type	Total Charge passed (coul.)	V _{FC} (ml)	V _C (ml)	V _{O₂} (ml)	α _C (ml/coul.)	V _{FA} (ml)	V _A (ml)	V _{H₂} (ml)	α _A (ml/coul.)	α _C /α _A
Cathode glow	150	21.0	44.4	7.8	0.156	10.5	10.5	Nil	—	—
Anode glow	300	42.0	42.0	Nil	—	21.0	26.4	3.6	0.018	8.7

$\alpha_C = (V_C - V_{FC}) / 150$ is the amount of non-Faradaic reaction at cathode per unit electricity

$\alpha_A = (V_A - V_{FA}) / 300$ is that at anode

$V_{FC} = \frac{2}{3} V_F$ —cathode gas volume according to Faraday's law

V_C = Vol of cathode gas actually liberated

V_{O_2} = Vol of oxygen in V_C . Other symbols have their usual significance.

Discussion

As in the case of cathode glow¹, the weight of evidence here too favours the idea of anode glow being a gas discharge phenomenon. The luminescent anode on the breakdown of normal electrolysis is enclosed in a sac of plasma through which current passes in the form of corona discharges resulting into luminescence. The envelope at the anode is composed of electrolyte entrained solvent vapour plus the ions, radicals and atoms produced by discharge through it. The idea is supported by results on spectral characteristics of anode glow^{6,8}. The colour and intensity of glow depend upon the nature of the species present in the plasma and their degree of excitation.

During conventional gas discharge phenomena in which an electric discharge is passed through some gas at low pressure between two metallic electrodes most of the voltage drop usually occurs in the cathode fall⁴. Further during production of corona discharges through a gas between cylinder and a co-axially placed wire, the breakdown field necessary is generally smaller when the wire is negative than when it is positive⁵. An analogous situation probably prevails in the glow discharge section of galvanoluminescence and appears to have a direct bearing on the preferential ease for the appearance of glow at cathode than at anode. Thus, if the film forms at the anode, cathode fall occurs on the solution side of the interface and the heat is dissipated in the solvent whereas if the film develops around the cathode, cathode fall occurs close to the electrode surface and heat is primarily dissipated in the cathode section where by greater excitation of the species in the film occurs resulting in stronger emission. So, the difference in two types of electrode glow seems to arise from the location of the section of glow-discharge in which major energy is expended.

The mechanism of chemical effects of anode glow is similar to that proposed for cathode glow². Thus the Faradaic part of the results is originated as usual by charge transfer processes and the non-Faradaic part by energy transfer processes occurring in the glow discharge section.

That the non-Faradaic yield during anode glow is less than during cathode glow under otherwise same conditions is consistent with availability of more energy in the discharge section when the glowing electrode is cathode rather than anode.

Thus, considering the electrode glow process as gas discharge phenomenon results of anode glow can be interpreted at least qualitatively.

References

1. S. K. SEN GUPTA and S. R. PALIT, *Indian. J. Phys.*, 1972, 46, 61.
2. S. K. SEN GUPTA and S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 91.
3. S. K. SEN GUPTA, Ph. D. Thesis, Calcutta University, 1973.
4. R. PAPOULAR 'Electrical Phenomena in Gases' (Trans. by B. Jeffrey) (Ed.) D. L. Jones, Illife Books Ltd, London, 1965, p. 127.
5. F. LLEWELLYN JONES, 'Ionization and Breakdown in Gases', Methuen Monograph, 1967.
6. T. BIAZ, J. C. VALOGNES and P. MERGAULT, *Compt. rend.*, Ser B, 1972, 275, 21.
7. K. ABRESCH and I. CLAASSEN, "Coulometric Analysis" Translated by L. L. Leveson, Chapman and Hall Ltd, London, 1960, p. 80.
8. J. GARBARZ-OLIVIER and C. GUILPIN, *J. Chim. Phys., Phys-Chim. Biol.*, 1975, 72, 207.